

Task 4.2A (subtask 2): Add support for additional ontology metadata to facilitate a better understanding of ontology content by the RADx community

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

Date (YYYY-MM-DD)	Version Number	Revision Reviewed / Approved By	Brief Description of Change
2025-04-03	v1	Document created by Michael Dorf (mdorf@stanford.edu) from the Stanford University Team.	Document created
2025-04-22	v1.1	Document written by Michael Dorf (mdorf@stanford.edu) from the Stanford University Team.	First draft completed
2025-04-28	v2	Document reviewed and approved by the Stanford team	

Purpose

The RADx Data Hub integrates BioPortal's biomedical ontologies to enhance the clarity and consistency of metadata for studies and data files. By adopting BioPortal's standardized terms, the RADx Data Hub enhances accuracy and interoperability of study data, making it easier to share and analyze these data across diverse studies. Task 4.2A aims to develop enhancements to the BioPortal [1,2] term functionality to facilitate ontology discovery, improve understanding of ontology terms, and promote the reuse of ontologies and terms by the RADx research community and the broader scientific community. Subtask 2 (or 4.2A-2) introduces new metadata attributes to ontologies and vocabularies that significantly enhance usability, serve as indicators of ontology quality, and reinforce the FAIR principles [7]—making ontologies more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.

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Introduction

The RADx Data Hub leverages BioPortal's comprehensive library of biomedical ontologies to standardize and present consistent metadata across its diverse studies. For RADx researchers and users, the accessibility of an established resource like BioPortal is crucial, not only for ensuring metadata uniformity but also for enhancing the ease with which data can be navigated and utilized.

A broad set of metadata attributes defining an ontology enhances the quality and utility of its content for RADx Data Hub research. Task 4.2A-2 introduces compatibility with FAIR-IMPACT's [3] *Metadata for Ontology Description and Publication Ontology* (MOD) v2.0 [4], which adds over 80 new metadata attributes for describing semantic resources. To support this, several new public REST API endpoints have been implemented, enabling full programmatic access to the expanded metadata functionality. Additionally, the BioPortal ontology creation and editing pages have been redesigned with a user-friendly, multi-tab interface that encourages users to provide comprehensive metadata, improving both completeness and quality.

Adopting the MOD framework further aligns BioPortal with the OntoPortal Alliance [5], promoting architectural and data-level interoperability across OntoPortal-based instances. It also streamlines future contributions to the shared, open-source OntoPortal codebase, ensuring consistency and maintainability across deployments. The following sections describe these improvements in detail.

New MOD-based metadata attributes

The latest update introduces a new set of metadata fields that conform to the most recent MOD specification. These attributes support a more granular and comprehensive description of ontologies, allowing researchers to work with semantic resources that adhere to the FAIR Principles—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. The principles emphasize machine-actionability (i.e., the capability of computational systems to find, access, interoperate, and reuse data with none or minimal human intervention) because humans increasingly rely on computational support to deal with data as a result of the increase in volume,

complexity, and creation speed of data. Figure 1 presents a class diagram of the MOD ontology, illustrating its broad coverage and detailed structure.

Figure 1: MOD ontology class diagram.

The orange boxes in Figure 1 represent core classes from the DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary) standard [8], such as *dcat:Catalog*, *dcat:Dataset*, *dcat:Distribution*, and related entities. These define the foundational structures for describing datasets, catalogs, services, and resources. The blue boxes represent MOD extensions to the DCAT classes. These MOD-specific classes, such as *mod:SemanticArtefact*, *mod:SemanticArtefactCatalog*, and *mod:SemanticArtefactDistribution*, introduce additional metadata properties tailored specifically for describing ontologies and semantic artifacts. They enrich the basic DCAT structures with ontology-specific attributes like competency questions, usage metrics, endorsements, modeling methodologies, and evaluation metrics.

Due to the significant increase in the scope of metadata within BioPortal ontologies, a new set of REST services was introduced to help researchers and developers discover the available attributes for ALL ontologies in BioPortal. Figure 2 captures a REST call to the service that returns all available metadata fields for an ontology. This lookup functionality is particularly valuable for software applications, which can use it to dynamically discover, interpret, and process metadata attributes without manual intervention. By enabling programmatic access to this structured metadata, the service allows systems to more effectively manage the growing volume and complexity of semantic data.

```

[
  - {
    @id: http://data.bioontology.org/ontology\_metadata/acronym,
    @type: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/OntologyMetadata,
    attribute: "acronym",
    namespace: "omv",
    label: null,
    extracted: "false",
    metadataMappings: null,
    - enforce: [
      "unique",
      "existence",
      "no_list"
    ],
    enforcedValues: null,
    category: "no",
    - @context: {
      @vocab: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/
    }
  },
  - {
    @id: http://data.bioontology.org/ontology\_metadata/name,
    @type: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/OntologyMetadata,
    attribute: "name",
    namespace: "omv",
    label: null,
    extracted: "false",
    metadataMappings: null,
    - enforce: [
      "unique",
      "existence",
      "no_list"
    ],
    enforcedValues: null,
    category: "no",
    - @context: {
      @vocab: http://data.bioontology.org/metadata/
    }
  },
]

```

Figure 2: Ontology metadata lookup REST service. This service returns a global list of metadata fields along with their associated properties, available across ALL ontologies in the system.

When querying individual ontologies via a REST endpoint, the new metadata fields and their corresponding values are now included in the output. Researchers and tool developers working across multiple ontologies and their versions can now compare the FAIR characteristics of each resource and devise their own strategies for prioritizing results based on accuracy and completeness of metadata. Figure 3 presents a sample output from the ontology REST service, using the *RADx Data Hub Ontology (DATAHUB)* [6] to demonstrate the newly available metadata attributes accessible to users.

```
- wasGeneratedBy: [
  "Protege editor"
],
wasInvalidatedBy: [ ],
pullLocation: https://data.bioontology.org/ontologies/DATAHUB/download?apikey=8b5b7825-538d-40e0-9e9e-5ab9274a9aeb,
isFormatOf: null,
hasFormat: [ ],
dataDump: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/DATAHUB/download,
csvDump: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/DATAHUB/download?download\_format=csv,
uriLookupEndpoint: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/search?ontologies=DATAHUB&require\_exact\_match=true&q=,
openSearchDescription: https://stagedata.bioontology.org/search?ontologies=DATAHUB&q=,
source: [ ],
- endpoint: [
  https://sparql.bioontology.org/ontologies/DATAHUB
],
includedInDataCatalog: [ ],
hasPriorVersion: null,
- hasPart: [
  https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/SARSMUTONTO,
  https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/COVID-19-ONT-PM
],
- ontologyRelatedTo: [
  https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/GECCO,
  https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/C19M
],
similarTo: [ ],
comesFromTheSameDomain: [ ],
- isAlignedTo: [
  https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/VCSR
],
isBackwardCompatibleWith: [ ],
- isIncompatibleWith: [
  https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/TM-SIGNS-AND-SYMPTS
],
hasDisparateModelling: [ ],
hasDisjunctionsWith: [ ],
- generalizes: [
  https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/IDO-COVID-19
],
explanationEvolution: [ ],
useImports: [ ],
- usedBy: [
  https://stagedata.bioontology.org/ontologies/70NMW-ADMTN-MD
]
```

Figure 3: RADx Data Hub (DATAHUB) [6] ontology metadata.

To facilitate metadata population, an extraction mechanism was implemented to automatically fill in key metadata fields using information from the ontology header. When a new ontology is submitted and processed, the system checks the header for metadata, extracts it, and automatically populates the corresponding fields. Figure 4 illustrates an example of metadata attributes found in the ontology's source OWL file.

```

<owl:Ontology rdf:about="https://github.com/bmir-radx/
radx-datahub-ontology">
  <owl:versionIRI rdf:resource="https://github.com/bmir-radx/
radx-datahub-ontology/blob/main/datahub-ontology.owl"/>
  <dc:contributor>Matthew Horridge</dc:contributor>
  <dc:contributor>Marcos Martinez Romero</dc:contributor>
  <dc:contributor>Martin O'Connor</dc:contributor>
  <dc:description xml:lang="en">The RADx Data Hub Ontology
provides a formally structured vocabulary to describe key
concepts within the RADx Data Hub.</dc:description>
  <dc:title xml:lang="en">RADx Data Hub Ontology</dc:title>
  <terms:license rdf:resource="http://creativecommons.org/licenses
/by/4.0/">
  <rdfs:comment xml:lang="en">The RADx Data Hub ontology is
licensed under CC BY 4.0 (https://creativecommons.org/licenses/
by/4.0/).</rdfs:comment>
</owl:Ontology>

```

Figure 4: Metadata fields auto-extracted from the ontology source file.

New ontology creation user interface

To support the expanded ontology metadata, the ontology creation user interface (UI) has been redesigned to offer a modern, intuitive, step-by-step experience that avoids overwhelming users with too many fields at once. It requests only the minimum necessary information required to create an ontology, enabling users to complete the task quickly and efficiently. Figures 5, 6, and 7 capture the three steps in the ontology creation process.

In **Step 1** (Figure 5), the interface requests the core required information about the ontology, including its name, acronym, categories, and visibility settings. Visibility can be set to either public or private, allowing submitters to control access. A public ontology is accessible to all users, while a private ontology is restricted to authorized users only, which can be useful for internal use or sensitive content.

Submit new ontology | NCBO x +

stage.bioontology.org/ontologies/new

BioPortal Ontologies Search Annotator Recommender Mappings Admin mdorf Support

Submit new ontology

← Details General Date and contacts

Name*

Acronym*

Visibility*
public

Administrators*
mdorf x

Categories

- Taxonomic_Classification Protein Phenotype Anatomy
- Animal_Gross_Anatomy Human Experimental_Conditions
- Subcellular_anatomy Chemical Neurological_Disorder
- Animal_Development Arabadopsis Other Neurologic_Disease
- Plant Cellular_anatomy_ All_Organisms Yeast Gross_Anatomy
- Plant_Development Biological_Process Upper_Level_Ontology
- Molecule Human_Developmental_Anatomy Genomic_and_Proteomic
- Fish_Anatomy Health Vocabularies Biomedical_Resources
- Immunology Cell Physicochemical Microbial_Anatomy
- Dysfunction Gene_Product Subcellular Mouse_Anatomy
- Plant_Anatomy Ethology Imaging Development

Groups

- radxdatahub CGIAR UMLS PSI CTSA caBIG
- OBO_Foundry BIBLIO BIS WHO-FIC

Is this ontology a view of another ontology?

Next >

Figure 5: Step 1 of 3 of the new ontology creation interface—Details section.

Step 2 (Figure 6) requests the general information, such as the ontology description, its representation language (OWL, OBO, or SKOS) as well as the source

file, which can either be uploaded directly or provided as a reference to a remote repository.

Submit new ontology | NCBO

stage.bioontology.org/ontologies/new

BioPortal Ontologies Search Annotator Recommender Mappings Admin mdorf Support

Submit new ontology

←

Details General Date and contacts

Edit the metadata of your ontology here. Some of these values are used by BioPortal functionalities, including for FAIRness assessment. See [guidelines and recommendations for metadata here](#).

Description ⓘ

Representation language* ⓘ

OWL

OWL ontologies submitted to BioPortal will be parsed by the OWL-API. An easy way to verify if your ontology will parse is to open it with the [Protégé](#) software which does use the same component.

Status ⓘ

production

Location*

Metadata Only
Allow Users

Load From Url
New Versions Loaded

Upload Local File

Drop your file here or, browse files on your device.

< Back Next >

Figure 6: Step 2 of 3 of the new ontology creation interface—General section.

The final **Step 3** (Figure 7) completes the ontology submission process by requesting the release date and contact information. Users are required to provide at least one contact name and email address, ensuring proper attribution and a point of communication for the ontology.

Figure 7: Step 3 of 3 of the new ontology creation interface—Date and contacts section.

New ontology editing user interface

Similar to the new ontology creation page, the ontology editing workflow has been redesigned to encourage the completion of as much metadata as possible in a user-friendly and efficient manner. Many metadata fields with constrained value sets have been presented with predefined options, providing users with an intuitive way to make their selections. Figure 8 displays the *General* section of the ontology metadata editing interface, highlighting an example of predefined Category field choices that are easily selectable by the user.

The screenshot shows the BioPortal interface for editing ontology metadata. The browser address bar indicates the URL: `stage.bioontology.org/ontologies/DATAHUB/submissions/4/edit?section=general`. The page title is "Edit Ontology Metadata".

The left sidebar contains a navigation menu with the following items: General (selected), Description, Dates, Licensing, Links, Media, Community, Usage, Relations, Content, Methodology, and Object description properties.

The main content area includes the following fields:

- Acronym***: DATAHUB
- Name***: RADx Data Hub Ontology
- Representation language***: OWL

A note below the representation language field states: "OWL ontologies submitted to BioPortal will be parsed by the OWL-API. An easy way to verify if your ontology will parse is to open it with the Protégé software which does use the same component."

The **Categories** section is highlighted with a red box and contains a grid of buttons for selecting ontology categories. The selected categories are **Taxonomic_Classification** and **Development**. Other visible categories include Protein, Phenotype, Anatomy, Animal_Gross_Anatomy, Human, Experimental_Conditions, Subcellular_anatomy, Chemical, Neurological_Disorder, Animal_Development, Arabadopsis, Other, Neurologic_Disease, Plant, Cellular_anatomy_, All_Organisms, Yeast, Gross_Anatomy, Plant_Development, Biological_Process, Upper_Level_Ontology, Molecule, Human_Developmental_Anatomy, Genomic_and_Proteomic, Fish_Anatomy, Health, Vocabularies, Biomedical_Resources, Immunology, Cell, Physicochemical, Microbial_Anatomy, Dysfunction, Gene_Product, Subcellular, Mouse_Anatomy, Plant_Anatomy, Ethology, and Imaging.

The **Groups** section includes buttons for radxdatahub, CGIAR, UMLS, PSI, CTSA, caBIG, OBO_Foundry, BIBLIO, BIS, and WHO-FIC.

The **Administrators*** section includes a text input field containing "admin x".

Figure 8: The General tab of the ontology editing interface that shows the easily selectable choices for the Category field of the RADx Data Hub (DATAHUB) [6] ontology.

The multi-faceted interface simplifies the process of updating an ontology by allowing users to edit any section of the metadata directly, without being constrained by a rigid step-by-step workflow. Figure 9 illustrates this flexibility: the user clicks on the Edit Ontology link and immediately navigates to the Community section, bypassing all previous sections.

Edit Ontology Metadata

General Bug database ⓘ

 Description
 Some ontology feedback and notes features are only possible if a GitHub repository is informed.

Dates Audience ⓘ

Licensing

Links Repository ⓘ

Media Mailing list ⓘ

Community

Usage

Relations To do list ⓘ

Content

Methodology Award ⓘ

Object description properties

Figure 9: The Community tab is an example of the multi-faceted interface that alleviates the need for a cumbersome sequential update workflow. The RADx Data Hub (DATAHUB) [6] ontology is used in the example above.

In summary, the UI updates introduced alongside the MOD-based metadata attributes were designed to make the seemingly daunting task of completing over 100 metadata fields [9] feel simple, manageable, and ultimately rewarding—resulting in a high-quality ontology ready to support any research and development efforts.

Resources

This section contains links to the source code developed as part of this task.

Github Repositories

- https://github.com/ncbo/bioportal_web_ui
- https://github.com/ontportal/ontportal_web_ui
- https://github.com/ontportal-lirimm/bioportal_web_ui

Issue Tracking

- [Implement enhancements to BioPortal's ontology term viewer for terms used in the RADx Data Hub](#)
- [AgroPortal and BioPortal code base alignment](#)
- [Feature: update UI of creating ontology and editing of its metadata - part 1 - UI Components](#)
- [Feature: update UI of creating ontology and editing of its metadata - part 2 - New Ontology and New Submission UI](#)
- [Feature: update UI of creating ontology and editing of its metadata - part 3 - Edit metadata new UI](#)
- [Feature: update UI of creating ontology and editing of its metadata - part 4 - Summary new UI](#)
- [Fix: remove the jquery validation for the ontology and submission creation](#)
- [Augment available metadata for various models](#)

References

[1] National Center for Biomedical Ontology. BioPortal. Accessed on April 14th, 2025. Available: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org>.

[2] Noy NF, Shah NH, Whetzel PL, Dai B, Dorf M, Griffith N, et al. BioPortal: ontologies and integrated data resources at the click of a mouse. Nucleic Acids Res 2009;37:W170-3. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkp440>.

- [3] FAIR-IMPACT. FAIR-IMPACT: Fostering FAIR data practices across domains. Accessed on April 14th, 2025. Available from: <https://fair-impact.eu/>
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